
A NEW LITERARY STYLE IN THE HISTORY OF PASHTO LITERATURE

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Abstract. As literature is a reminder of social life, it is related to human society and life. Interpretation of human feelings, thoughts, and emotions is a task in the literature. Style in literature is the characteristic of an artist's or writer's works that distinguishes them from the works of other writers. Here, too, the author portrays internal and external feelings and thoughts in his works. The concept of word style is the same as the old concept because it shows itself in a new form in every aspect of life throughout history. The poet and the writer are also part of society; they take the raw material (Suze) from society and combine it with the sweetness of literature through language, to impress the reader with literary taste. Therefore, the style and method of expression of each poet and writer are different, which is called literary style. The Pashto language is also one of those historical languages that has seen many changes, high and deep throughout history. Various styles have emerged in different historical periods, such as: Roshni's style, Khushal Khan's style, Abdul Hamid Momand's style, Abdul Rahman Baba's style, New literary's style and so on. The subject of my article is a new literary style in the history of Pashto literature. Style is discussed more in writing, research, and writing than speaking and speech because it is important to diagnose and identify style in writing. Thus, the properties and characteristics of the style, along with recognition of the literary period, help clarify the message of a literary work.

Keywords: Style, Literary work, Literature, Genres and Literary Schools.

Introduction

Certainly, literary history is an important branch of general history, and political and social history also helps literary history. Therefore, the literary's history of the literature of a language describes all the evolutions that have happened to the language throughout history. The nation's intellectual excellence and academic progress are recorded in different stages of history. According to Professor Habibi Sahib: (The history of a nation's literature is actually the history of the nation's rationality, academic excellence, it's the history of important stages of life.) [1:31]

This is literature history, which investigates the height and depth of the language in relation to the conditions of time and era, shows us the goodness of literary works with beauties of language and literary; In this filed, it is related to the worldview,

ideology and style of the writer and poet. In different periods of history, different genres have emerged, after which, slowly, some styles have found followers and turned into literary schools. Because style is one of the characteristics of a literary work, a work can be distinguished from similar works using this style. Because style is one of the characteristics of a literary work, literary works can be distinguished from similar works by means of this style. The subject of this article is the new literary style, which is related to the fourth period of the history of Pashto literature. Signs of a new school of literature and a new style in Pashto poetry and literature appeared after the arrival of British colonialism and Western technology, the author of the theory of literature writes (which showed its full effect in the fourteenth century). In the contents of these writings and poems, the passions of swordsmanship, bravery, ethnicity, and nationalism have been brought in a large amount, in which the spirit of protecting freedom and independence is in motion. In the writings, the new life and new thought came into movement in both parts of one body (Pakhtunkhwa), the morale of progress and development was revived, and the flag of independence was raised in poetry and literature. The heads in Koza Pakhtunkhwa: Fazl Mahmood Makhfi, Mohammad Akbar Khadim and Abdul Akbar Khan and others, a group of former teachers of Pashto appeared in Barah Pakhtunkhwa (Afghanistan), such as: Prof. Habibi, Prof. Rashtin, Ustad Alfat, Ustad Khadim, Majroh, Benwa and others. In the end, I raise my hands to pray to my Allah, who has made the issue effective and useful for readers. [2:43]

Goals

The history of Pashto literature presents information about the new style. We gathered all the contexts of the scholars of Pashto literature who have given their votes, and it has become clear that the new literary style in the history of Pashto literature begins with the freedom of Afghanistan.

Method and Materials

As each writing is created in a specific method and procedure, in addition to the field of library, descriptive method has been used in exploring this academic article.

A new literary style in the history of Pashto literature

Before talking about the new literary style of the Pashto language, I would like to provide basic information about the style; Indeed, according to Mr. Rohi, "A language can progress when academic and literary works are written in that language." [3:82] As knowledge of literary styles is essential materials for every writer and poet, without style the literary work of the writer does not have any value; style is the word of the Arabic language, which literally means to cut gold and silver and put it in a mold; however, the term refers to a special type and mode of speaking and writing. Europeans use the word style for Mode; the ancient Persian writers would have used other words such as art, style, context, method, mode, manner and

etc. However, now the word of style is very useful. According to the author of the literature research book, "the style is composed of two elements, the idea and the personality of the writer, whenever there are no two people in the human society who have the same personality; That's why we can't find the same styles. Even the personality of a man is not the same at different times and under different circumstances. According to Newman, "A style is a thought expressed in language." [3:84] The author of the theory of literature, however, in a general and common way, has divided the style into three types: First, individual or special and personal style: this is the style of the poet and writer, which is completely separate from other poets and writers. Although not all poets and writers have a special style, but some writers and poets have tried different ways throughout their literary lives. Therefore, this was called his special style. For example, in the prose and literary writings of Gul Pacha Alfat, we can see some writing characteristics that can be called the author's special style. Second-Periodical style: Common linguistic, semantic, rhetorical, and syntactical features and other distinguishing factors in a certain literary period; for example, the similarities in the literary works of the Dari language of the third, fourth, and fifth centuries of Hijra, which they have given together the name of the Khorasani Style. Third - Literary style: This is the style that is in front of the academic, historical, religious, and other styles and, in common, the style of ordinary speech. The differences between literary style and other styles are in the language of poetry and literature.

As the Pashto language is also a historical language, it has gone through different stages in different periods of history, and with the passing and change of time, various literary flows have come into being under the light of different literary methods; then, each style has turned into a literary school as a result of the great follow of the followers. Examples of which are the literary school of Roshanians', the literary school of Khushal Khan's, the literary school of Abdul Rahman Baba's, the literary school of Hamid Baba's and Kazem Khan Shida's, the new literary school, etc. [5:202] The subject of this article is the new literary style in Pashto literature history, which has been adopted by many writers. As a result, a new literary school has emerged. A new literary style appeared in Pashto literature at the time when the fourth literary period of Pashto literature history began, which is called modern or contemporary literature. The ancient period of the Pashto literature history, the author of the book, Mr. Zewar Sahib, writes: "The fourth period has started from (1250 AH), which is the era of (Muhammadzo)" Now we want to clarify when contemporary literature begins, according to Mr. Rohi, "According to some literary experts, all literary flows can be divided into three types: Folkloric literature, classical literature and modern (new or contemporary) literature". - Folkloric literature that meets the interests of the people; the author is unknown; it is passed down from one generation

to another. Classical literature is literature on educated people. The word classic is derived from the word classicus, which means first degree in Latin; some have other meanings as well. For example, the literature that is timeless, appreciated at any time and in any place, Greek and Roman literature, literature that was written following Greek and Roman literature, literature that is taught in class, and ancient literature that is not modern or contemporary. Contemporary literature in the Pashto language refers to literature that has inspired the industrial, social, political, and cultural phenomena of modern life in new images and is a reflection of the concepts, desires, values, and ideals of the current era. [2:43]

According to Mr. Rohi: Contemporary Pashto literature began with the publication of the (Afghan) newspaper in Pakhtunkhwa around 1910. In this newspaper, new genres of Pashto literature were introduced and the writers and poets like Rahat Zakheli, Fazal Mohammad Mukhfi and Abdul Akbar Khan Akbar planted the seeds of contemporary literature, Here I would like to summarize the following three steps from Rohi Sahib's book: With the publication of Siraj-ul-Akhbar for the second time (1911) in Afghanistan, the foundation of contemporary Pashto literature was laid. Contemporary Pashto literature in Afghanistan reached stages of enlightenment, growth, and transition. The followers of contemporary literature have adopted the way that, in their poems and writings, there are signs that are different from the previous writings. With the arrival of the 20th century, the mental and physical conditions of Afghanistan were prepared. At the same time, cultural objects, such as factories, printing houses, hospitals, modern tools, and work tools, show modern life. (2:50) With the change in traditional life, new ideas were born, people with modern education who were exiled came with new ideas and a mental outline of a new lifestyle, and contemporary literature was put at the service of society as committed and responsible literature. With the publication of Siraj-ul-Akhbar, the foundation is also provided for the development of the Pashto literature. At that time, many young people in Larah and Barah Pakhtunkhwa had studied new sciences and European literature; they had known new literary genres and forms. They marked the way to express their thoughts, that is, which started the modern Palace of Literature on the ancient foundation of Pashto.

Literary innovators at that time consciously wanted to use literature as an effective tool for national goals. The subject of the literature at this time was patriotism, demand for independence, condemnation of corruption, condemnation of bigotry, dissemination of positive science and technology and new culture, consolidation of national unity, alignment of traditions and assumptions with the demands of modern life, the uprising of Muslim nations in the east against British colonialism, and other national, Islamic, and human aspirations. In the literature of this stage, the message and commitment are very strong, and not much attention has

been paid to the form; most of the poems of the first phase of contemporary Pashto literature are devoted to patriotism. During the Enlightenment period, the heads of contemporary literature: Maulvi Saleh Muhammad Kandahari, Ghulam Muhyiddin Afghan, Maulvi Abdul Wasi Kandahari, Abdul Ali Mustaghni, Abdul Hadi Dawi, Mahmoud Tarzi and others... [2:52]

This stage of intelligence is mostly related to the political movement of Waish Zalmiyan. Almost all famous writers and poets of the Pashto language were included in the political organization of Waish Zalmiyan. Therefore, most poems and writings of the intelligence period have social and political forms. The clause of (promoting the Pashto language) is also included in the decree of Waish Zalmiyan. The literary method of the intelligence stage is critical realism, which has been shown in different genres of poetry, short stories, literary pieces, dramas, satires, and literary articles, which mainly reflect the struggle against corruption, oppression, and exploitation. The literature on the intelligence stage is very different in terms of message and idea, creatively and artistically, so it can be said that the literary method of contemporary literature is realism, but it is simple because it does not have complex techniques. On the other hand, in terms of nature, it works well for publicity. Writers and poets of the last stage (Abdul Hai Habibi, Siddiqullah Rishitin, Gul Pacha Alfat, Qiyamuddin Khadim, Abdul Rauf Benwa, Abdul Shakur Rashad, Bahauddin Majroh, Muhammad Musa Shafiq, Abdul Rahman Pajhwok, Muhammad Siddique Pasrali, Habibullah Tashi, Muhammad Jan Fana, Abdullah Bakhtani, Mujar Ahmed Ziyar, Sulaiman Laeeq and Talib Kandahari and others. [2:90] - In addition to the literary method of critical realism in the literature of the transition period, socialist realism also hit the blades, the literature of the transition, which was the motivator of the ideology of the working class and laborers. The main idea of the poems, stories, critical observations, and literary research at that time was the struggle against feudalism and imperialism, and for social justice, development, peace, and internationalism. The authors of the transition phase are: (Sulaiman Laeeq, Mujawar Ahmed Ziyar, Habibullah Zarh Sawand, Abdullah Bakhtani, Ibrahim Atai, Dost Shinwari, Abdul Raouf Qateel, Afzal Takkur, Latif Behand and others. [2:147-149] According to Mr. Zawar Sahib: The fourth literary period begins with the independence of Afghanistan. This literary period comprises several stages. The A- In this literary period, Pashto literature did not remain unaffected. At this time, the industrial period of European civilization began started and British colonialism in India was strengthened. influence of the new civilization and industry also reached India. Roads and railway lines were built all over India, new education and schools were also increased, and newspapers and magazines were published in English and Indian languages. Printing presses, libraries, and other means of publication were accelerated. Britain invaded Afghanistan in 1839. The effect of this political flood was also important in Pashto literature and

culture; therefore, both Pashto prose and poetry came under these effects. The fluent and idiomatic writing in prose, which Khushal Khan laid the foundation for, became popular, and some Pashto books also appeared in this way. Also, when the world war started in 1914, the eastern states were also afraid and the idea of freedom was born in all nations. In order to promote this idea, the Pashtuns living in India, Iran, Turkey and Egypt as well as in the eastern parts of Afghanistan, who were influenced by British colonialism, felt a sense of freedom. And they brought freedom and patriotism to Pashto literature and there was a change in Pashto literature. The translation movement in Pashto poetry and prose also started. Mulla Nomanuddin Ahmad Kakakhil translated Ibn Battuta's travelogue and Qazi Abdul Qadir Peshawari military names and terms from English to Pashto. Ghulam Muhammad Popalzi edited Maulana Hali Madu Jazar Islam in Pashto and Munshi Ahmed Jan translated the history of Afghanistan from English to Pashto. Such translation also brought with it new ideas and the foundations of a new civil life. The direction of artistic literature was also taken up, replacing the Sonnet with the basic problems of life, and provided the background for political poetry.

B- After Afghanistan gained its independence, a new literary era began, one in which Pashtun authors and poets made great advancements in the language and literature. A group of people known as Pashto Interviews developed during this period. There are multilingual dictionaries and grammars produced by this community. The first Pashto magazine was produced by a Pashto organization that was founded in Kandahar in 1311 A.H. After moving to Kabul in 1316 A.H., a Pashto community was created there. Many novels were published in this neighborhood. The whole issue of Kabul Magazine in 1320 AH was written in Pashto. The Ministry of Education produced several publications in Pashto. At this time, the Tolo-Afghan and Eastern Union newspapers in Kandahar were published in Pashto, while the Waraangi, Sistan, and Mewand newspapers were published in Paktia, Farah, and Gershak. There were several poets and authors schooled there, and the literary works of the time provide news of fresh life, the greatest ideas, scholarly investigations, literary observations, and other interesting gems. In Koza Pakhtunkhwa, it's also important to highlight the Peshawar Pashto Academy, Noshaar Literary Jirga, Literary Community, Bazm Literature, Abdul Rahman Baba Literary Jirga, and Quetta Literary Association. The completion of Pashto's legendary capital is intriguing; there are distinct changes from earlier times. [4:42] The creator of the Department of Literature claims: When British colonization and Western technology arrived here, the beginnings of a new literary school and style were visible. The Department of Literature's author claims that "it displayed its full power in the fourteenth century. The poetry has considerably rekindled the desires for swordplay, courage, ethnicity, and nationalism, and they have infused the movement with the

spirit of pursuing and defending independence and freedom. The movement in the flower garden of literature saw a new spring when Ghazi Amanullah Khan won the country's freedom; contemporary life and fresh perspectives have arrived, and these perspectives are shining both inside and outside of Pakhtunkhwa.

The author of the Department of Literature wrote, "The sense of patriotism, progress and development found strength and the spirit of national enthusiasm and patriotism entered Pashto poetry and literature." The independence movement started in Pakhtunkhwa and its effects were felt in poetry and literature. (In Koza Pakhtunkhwa, Fazal Mahmood Makhfi, Mohammad Akbar Khadim and Abdul Akbar Khan are the heads, in Bura Pakhtunkhwa (Afghanistan) a group of former teachers of Pashto appeared, such as Alfat, Khadim, Majroh, Habibi, Benwa, Rishitin and others....) (6:282) The author of Theory of Literature book says: (In my opinion, the nominal representatives of the new school of literature in Koza Pakhtunkhwa are: Hamza, Samudar, Syed Rasool Rasa, Ghani Khan, Ajmal Khattak and others, and these people hold the position of teachers in Afghanistan. They are: Habibi, Alfat, Majroh, Khadim, Benwa and Rishitin.) The author of the literary schools, Mr. Rishitin Sahib, has shown the characteristics of the new literary school as follows:

1- Modern life, new world, new thoughts have been expressed in this literary school and Western literature has entered Pashto literature.

2- Tribal and national songs, national anthems, passionate songs and Pashtunoli and ethnicity cries and yells have increased.

3- Condemnation of foreign colonialism, tyranny, oppression and excessive force, as well as intellectual and pen struggle against usury, bribery and other social evils are considered the best features of this school.

4- Protecting the rights of workers, farmers and laborers and preventing injustice and inequality from the society is a clear sign of the literary works and thoughts of this literary school.

5- The shows of new civilization, culture, cinema and dance have increased.

6- Motivations for political awakening, parties, struggle for revolution, change, democracy and self-government have increased in poetry and literature.

7- Criticism and critical observation, truthful speech, bravery and fluent speech are also clearly portrayed in poetry and literature.

8- Along with the obvious spiritual change in the poetry and literature of this period, words, phrases, interpretations, change, increase and newness have also emerged.

9- In this school, the literary and academic capital has increased a lot in terms of quality and quantity, namely from the side of "how much and how". [5:238-240].

The author of the Department of Literature writes: In the current literary era, a few small literary schools have also been established. In Pakhtunkhwa, Amir Hamza

Shinwari and Syed Rasool Rasa Aram and Qar literature school became very famous and besides, Ghani and Ajmal Joshnak and Mastana schools were also famous. Here in Afghanistan, many Zalmyans joined the poetic group of Ulfat and Khadim and Benwa's Mastana Bazm. but it is necessary to mention here that in these thirty and forty years, the Kabul Pashto Community (established in 1316) has made many efforts for the explanations and publications of Pashto literature and culture. He has published a large number of poems and articles on the advancement and development of Pashtun culture and literature. also, Peshawar Pashto Academy (established in 1955) has also fully participated in this way, which is full of Kabul and Pashto magazines. These poems and literary writings have a valuable place in the structure, growth and development of the new and contemporary literary school of Pashto.

A comparison of the contemporary literary trends in Pashto literature with those in foreign literature

Here, we contrast the new Pashto literary form with a variety of other forms, including: Literary techniques and genres have changed concurrently with the profound changes in Russian society during the past few decades. There is a common belief that serious literature has lost its attraction to most readers in the present social environment and that mainstream culture, with its focus only on entertainment, has won the day. The capacity of serious literature to survive in a market economy is threatened by the large distance between its writers and the average reader. However, some authors appear to have discovered a formula for popularity with readers without sacrificing the creative integrity of their novels. Among them is Marina Judeni. (12) Five years ago, B. Akunin's name first debuted on the Russian literary scene. As a well-known man of letters, translator, and expert on Japanese language and culture, author Grigory Tkhartishvili's works are now widely available in translation, including in Norway and Sweden. [11]. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, literary representatives from Nakhchivan engaged in study on the Publicistic literary movement. This article examines their research. It emphasizes the important role authors have had in developing the literary language used in the press, concentrating in particular on the linguistic characteristics of the Publicistic style employed in Azerbaijan. During the second half of the 19th century, the work of renowned thinkers contributed to the development of the Publicistic style. The journal "Akinchi," which was founded on enlightened ideals, had a significant influence on the nation's intellectuals, especially in the area of word invention. The newspapers gave the local language first priority when creating new terms, relying on readers' day-to-day experiences and blending their chosen terminology into the literary language of the century. [1] Li Oufan and David Der-wei Wang's discussion of the "modernity of the late Qing Dynasty" had a significant impact on academic circles in mainland China. As a result, many mainland scholars started to study the literature of

the late Qing Dynasty from the perspective of "modernity", expanding the narrative range of modern literary history and reshaping research perspectives. The author uses Li Oufan and David Der-wei Wang as examples to explore how literary history changed in response to the "Modernity" Model. (19) William Wordsworth, one of the finest English poets, might also be seen as an example of the new style. One of England's finest poets, William Wordsworth, is referred to as the poet of nature. His poetry become more important in English literature. The goal of this article is to demonstrate my appreciation for him by examining the factors that led to the development of such a lyrical style and the manner in which he sang highly of nature to communicate his ideals. [9]

Globalization and universal themes have given rise to new fields of literary study. The literature of American Indians has a very deep history, and modern and postmodern American literature may be traced back to it. There are numerous literary indications that American Indian culture, rites, and ceremonies have had a significant impact on American culture, literature, and globalization of literature. This has led to the creation of a particular type of multicultural literature that reflects, despite the fact that the majority of the American Indians' oral literature and their universal concepts have not been recorded. (14) One such example is the way certain authors subvert their subject matter by fusing exalted Classical, Biblical, or Romantic ideas with occasionally informal, conversational tones. By disorienting the reader, these strategies can enhance their intuitive response to the material. Thus, stylistic interpretative techniques become essential in literature classes, whether they are taught in first or second languages. (13) One major source of conflict between linguistic approaches to literariness and other activities in the field, such as text-editing and literary biography, is the propensity of literary stylisticians to ignore the author's contribution to the creation of literary meaning. (4) Nathaniel Hawthorne's use of narrative method signaled an important turning point in American writing. The American Revolution opened the door for a new age by releasing society from the restrictions of Puritan traditions and beliefs. The divide grew even wider as American Romanticism recognized the author's distinctive voice. Hawthorne tried to depict the sociological, economic, and political changes he saw throughout his lifetime in his writings. [17]

Discussion

The beginning of contemporary Pashto literature can be traced to the arrival of the British in India, according to the following theories, which Mr. Rohi has succinctly explained in his book (History of Pashto literature)'s second volume: 1- Western literature was adopted by the British in India and brought to Pashto, according to Rohi Sahib: "Probably the proponents of this theory rely on this point; This argument is refuted by the fact that the East India Company was founded by

Britain in India around 1600, but the effect of western literature on Pashto language was not felt until approximately 1910. The important thing is that it is related in the Pashto literary history. From (1338 AD) to the publication of (Siraj Al-Akhbar), contemporary literary patterns were not visible in the pages of Pashto literary history. Contemporary Pashto literature starts with the British invasion of Afghanistan (1839), but it is important that it is related in the Pashto literary history. Apart from Hanan Barakzai and a few others, that was not great poet has passed in this period. "Hanan is also a student and follower of Hamid Baba's school of literature". 3- The beginning of Pashto contemporary literature is found in the second period of the reign of Amir Sher Ali Khan. There is no doubt that in the middle of the 19th century, a new movement and dynamism is shining in the traditional life of Afghans. The modernization movement got underway, the daily Shams Nahar was founded, and improvements were achieved in both administrative and military issues during the second Amir Sher Ali Khan era (1886–1888). The formalization of Pashto led to the creation of the Tuhfa Al-Amir grammar, which was used to teach the language. However, there are no indications of modern literature at this time. 4- Maulvi Ahmed established the groundwork for Pashto artistic writing in the seventh decade of the nineteenth century. His prose is undeniably elegant and charming, but it contains stories from folklore rather than a reflection of modern life. 5- Although no poem or narrative from this time period may be used as a model, some authors believe that contemporary writing began in the year of independence (1919). 6. According to the proponents of this idea, contemporary Pashto literature dates back to the year 1350 AH, however this refers to the Anno Hegirae year. They claim that Munshi Ahmad Jan is the father of contemporary writing. In actuality, Munshi Ahmad Jan's writing style is both beautiful and intriguing in terms of form and comparable to Maulvi Ahmad's in terms of content. Mr. Ruhi asserts that contemporary Pashto literature dates back to the 1910s, when an Afghan newspaper began appearing in Pakhtunkhwa. New Pashto literary subgenres were launched in this publication, where authors and poets like Rahat Zakheli, Fazal Mohammad Mukhfi, and Abdul Akbar Khan Akbar sowed the literary seeds of the modern age. The groundwork for current Pashto literature was created with the second Afghan printing of Siraj-ul-Akhbar in 1911. There are three stages of modern Pashto literature in Afghanistan: enlightenment, progress, and transition.

Result and Conclusion

Since Pashto literature is rich in both poetry and prose, mode is used figuratively to refer to a particular form of both poetry and prose. Additionally, each poet and writer prefer a certain approach or style, and each speaker approaches poetry in a unique way. The term "style" is often employed in numerous sectors of the arts, including art literature, painting, sculpture, architecture, and calligraphy. When

Afghanistan gained its independence and Western technology arrived, a new literary style in Pashto literature evolved. Literature was employed as a powerful instrument. The topics of literature at this time were different: patriotism, the demand for independence, corruption, condemnation of bigotry, dissemination of positive science and technology and new culture, consolidation of national unity, alignment of traditions and assumptions with the demands of modern life, the uprising of Muslim countries in the east against British colonialism, and other national, Islamic, and human aspirations. The Enlightenment Stage, the Growth Stage, and the Transition Stage are Rohi Sahib's three divisions of the present literary epoch. According to Mr. Hashmi: Modern living and fresh ideas swept throughout Pakhtunkhwa after freedom was attained during the authority of Amanullah Khan. A new literary movement also emerged at this time. The independence movement began in Pakhtunkhwa, and its impacts were seen in poetry and literature. The spirit of nationalism, progress, and growth gained power. Fazal Mahmood Mukhfi, Mohammad Akbar Khadim, Abdul Akbar Khan, Rahat Zakheli, and others are standing in the front row of this field, and a number of former Barah Pakhtunkhwa (Afghanistan) professors as well as other persons, including Alfat, Habibi, Benwa, Rishitin, Khadim, Majroh, and others, have arrived. Each of them has a distinct writing or poetic style, and today a new literary school has been named to encompass all of those styles. Many other authors and poets now emulate them and their work.

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